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DESIGNING GOOD PRACTICES FOR TEACHING AND MANAGING MULTI-CAMPUS COURSES

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ABSTRACT

In 2016, our university college merged with several other educational institutions to form a multi-campus university. Mergers and clustering of universities have been a European trend over the past decade, and although the trend has now flattened out, such restructuring processes are still ongoing. In the wake of mergers follows a restructuring at many levels. Teachers involved in the Bachelor of Engineering education at our multi-campus university faced the challenge of developing and aligning courses for 1000 students across three different campuses located far apart.

The Department of Physics is responsible for a first-year introductory course in physics and chemistry, which is mandatory for all Bachelor of Engineering studies: 11 study programs under four different faculties in three cities. A team of nine physics and/or chemistry teachers deliver the course to students, most of whom are on-campus students while a minority follows the course online. In this paper we focus on experiences from the teacher collaboration, involving the preliminary design process and the practical implementation of the course during the spring term of 2020 before the COVID-19 outbreak. The students were asked for their perspective in an online survey, the results of which are reported and discussed.

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As a result of the collaboration between the nine teachers at three campuses, all teaching resources used in the course are made available to teachers and all enrolled students across campuses – an approach much appreciated by the students. This open, full-access approach shows, that even though the teaching material was harmonized in the preliminary phase, teachers are presenting the same topic somewhat differently. This gives room for further development and collaboration.

1 INTRODUCTION

Mergers and clustering of universities have been a worldwide trend over the past decade, and in Europe there was a peak between 2013 and 2015. Although the rate is now decreasing, such restructuring processes are still ongoing, e.g. in France, Lithuania and Greece [1].

In 2016 our multi-campus university was formed as a merger between a larger university (Norwegian University of Science and Technology) and three smaller university colleges. One of the overall intentions behind the merger of the four institutions was to provide a better and more comprehensive education of high standard [2]. Case studies from Northern Europe have identified similar rationales behind mergers in other parts of the world: a desire for efficiency and effectiveness. However, in the Nordic countries, arguments of better quality and excellence of education tend to carry heavier weight [3]. When it comes to the degree of integration between the merging institutions it depends of the purpose behind the merge. Some *“...mergers are more “federal” by character with the merged units remaining largely intact yet within part of a much larger organisation. Arguably, in the short term, these mergers are easier to manage and implement but with less obvious added value for the parties involved. Other cases display a high ambition from the outset”* [3, p. 231]. In our university we see both aspects represented, the government wanted to reduce the number of institutions in higher education, while the actual merge however showed a wish for integrating the four institutions into a new institution [2]. Geschwind et. al. [3] also points out that the distance between the campuses and cultural differences can play a crucial role regarding the success of the merge. The geographical obstacle is an obvious challenge in our case, while cultural the teachers involved in the Bachelor of Engineering programs have a lot in common since they all came from the university colleges.

2 BACKGROUND

Before the merger, the three university colleges were located at separate campuses in cities 300-400 km apart, corresponding to a car drive of 5-6 hours – as illustrated in Fig. 1. The teachers involved in the Bachelor of Engineering education at our multi-campus university therefore faced the challenge of developing and aligning courses for approximately 1000 students across three different campuses located considerable distances apart.

Fig. 1. The three campuses, separated by distances of 300 to 400 km.

The Department of Physics was responsible for restructuring a mandatory first-year introductory course in physics and chemistry for all 11 Bachelor of Engineering study programs, representing four different faculties in three cities. A substantial amount of the students has a vocational education background, requiring one- or two-semester qualifying courses before starting an engineering education. At Campus A and B, some of the students take qualifying courses in parallel with engineering studies, while campus B and C offer qualifying courses which are not part of the Bachelor of Engineering studies. Before the merger, the first-year introductory course in physics and chemistry was delivered identically to all study programs at campus A and B, whereas campus C had five slightly different courses, tailored to specific study programs. Campus A was unique in offering courses for online students as well as on-campus classes.

The design of the new course thus had to take into account differences in students' educational backgrounds; offer study program-specific learning modules; and make allowance for both on-campus and online students. These requirements translated into the following modular course structure:

- Common chemistry module (2,5 credits): Atomic structure and the periodic table, stoichiometry, chemical equilibrium, acids and bases.
- Common physics module (5,0 credits): Classical mechanics, rotational dynamics, oscillatory motion.
- Study program-specific modules (2,5 credits):
 - Fluid mechanics and physics of waves (for students of building engineering and mechanical engineering).
 - Electromagnetism (for students of electronics; renewable energy; logistics engineering; materials engineering; chemical engineering).

The chemistry module is common to all study programs except materials and chemical engineering, for whose students the chemistry module consisted entirely of electrochemistry. The new course is offered at campuses A, B and C in 3 different module combinations, with identical expected learning outcomes and a final exam with the same classical mechanics part.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Course predesign – developing a culture for collaboration

The alignment of the first-year course in physics and chemistry was a part of a unification initiative for all Bachelor of Engineering study programs at the three previous university colleges, also involving mathematics courses and an Introduction to engineering course. This process culminated in draft versions of the relevant courses, based on input from the Bachelor of Engineering study programs.

The three university colleges had a similar academic tradition and culture in terms of course content and approach to teaching, which facilitated the alignment process. Despite geographical distances and lack of convenient travel routes, physical rather than virtual meetings were held at each campus in turn, with both involved teachers and administrative staff in attendance.

After the start-up phase in the spring 2019, the development of the physics and chemistry course continued over the autumn term in online meetings using collaborative tools. The underpinning strategy was to facilitate a culture of collaboration, in which decisions were made through team processes, rather than unilaterally at each campus.

3.2 Resource sharing

Our university mandates the use of a specific learning management system (LMS) to manage courses. Traditionally each course has its separate “space” or virtual “room” inside the LMS, to which only enrolled students and teachers have access. Our course consists of several separate courses, each with its own coordinator. To maximize transparency for students and teachers, a shared and open “virtual room” was set up on the LMS, as shown in Fig. 2 below.

Fig. 2. The design of the resources at the learning management system.

Information common to all students is located in one folder, as illustrated by the green box. Lecture notes, presentations etc. specific to each individual course is put in folders corresponding to a specific campus to which all students and teachers at any campus have access (this illustration is a simplification since more than one version of the course exists per campus). The principle of having everything open to anyone enrolled in the course gives full transparency, which is an important aspect since learning goals and the final exams are the same across the campuses.

3.3 The questionnaire

An online questionnaire was constructed to survey student experiences with this multi-campus course, with questions based on input from all the teachers involved. The questions were intended to detect campus differences in student satisfaction with on-campus teaching, and also to map how, and to what extent, students used shared learning resources.

The questionnaire received 188 answers from a total of approx. 900 enrolled students, giving a response rate of 20 %. It was published shortly after all Norwegian educational institutions closed their campuses following the COVID-19 outbreak mid-March 2020, at which point all classes were moved online. The questionnaire specified that all questions concerned the situation before the corona virus outbreak, when on-campus classes were still running normally.

The structure of the questionnaire used is detailed below:

- Student background (study program; specific course enrolment; whether on-campus/online student; gender)
- Experiences from chemistry and physics classes, respectively
 - Level of satisfaction with on-campus classes
 - Rate of usage of shared resources and learning material available from the LMS (with answer categories of “Often”; “Sometimes” and “Never”), and students’ level of satisfaction with these resources

4 RESULTS

One item on the questionnaire concerned the usage of resources shared between campuses: lecture notes and video recordings from campus A. The rationale was to uncover the extent to which students used resources from their own lecturer and material from other lecturers/campuses, respectively. The results are summarized in Fig. 3:

Shared resources usage, by campus

Fig. 3. Usage of different types of shared resources in physics and chemistry, by campus. Campus A produced lecture recordings to which all enrolled students had access. Percentages of students are the sum of percentages in categories "Often used" and "Sometimes used" the shared resource.

The majority of students preferred lecture notes from their own lecturer (in both physics and chemistry, the blue and green columns). The exception was campus B, where students expressed preference for lecture notes made by others. In the comments field of the questionnaire, students who preferred lecture notes from other lecturers cited language issues as one reason, as their own lecturer predominantly used lecture notes in English. Lecture video recordings were produced at campus A, and students at campus A used these recordings more than students from other campuses.

The following two comments from students illustrate perceived benefits and drawbacks of consulting study materials produced by other teachers:

- [On why he/she appreciates lecture notes by other teachers] «*Difficult to connect the dots when the textbook and PowerPoints are in English, while lectures are held in Norwegian.* »
- [On watching lecture recordings from campus A] «*Lecturers from the various campuses have different backgrounds and areas of expertise, and approach topics differently, using unique teaching styles. This makes it harder for me to follow other lecturers with whom I'm not familiar.* »
- [On why he/she appreciates lecture notes by other teachers] «*I like having access to the notes from all the lecturers, it gives you access to more examples and different explanations.* »

Regarding the general use of the LMS, some students claim that there is too much information available. On the other hand, some students appreciate the shared resources and asked for the same transparent LMS-design in other multi-campus courses.

5 DISCUSSION

Since this course was run for the first time, teacher collaboration was mostly on a practical and administrative level, as opposed to a pedagogical level. While some study materials were produced during the course pre-design phase, a considerable amount of lecture notes, assignments etc. were produced continuously as the semester progressed. Time constraints limited the amount of pedagogical discussion between teachers once the semester had started.

The teachers involved had different backgrounds and areas of expertise, and the working hypothesis in the planning stage was that the diversity in teaching methodology, teaching style and approach to topics would let teachers complement each other. However, it's evident from Fig. 3 that students only to a limited extent consulted study materials made by other teachers. As indicated in a student comment, teacher non-uniformity was seen as an impediment to learning, as students take time to get used to a particular teaching style. The interpersonal student-teacher relationship appears important for making students relate to the online learning resources, as students in the questionnaire expressed preference for recordings of their own lecturer. The importance of this relationship is higher than we expected and should be addressed in the future as a potential barrier for learning when using online materials.

Given that all enrolled students would be subjected to the same exam, transparency was the main rationale for having a shared virtual "room" in the LMS. From the teachers' perspective, a shared "room" would enable uniformity and synchronization between lecturers teaching the same topics. Even though this article concerns the situation before the COVID-19 outbreak, the shared space proved very useful once all classes moved online when the campuses were shut down: The extra workload with producing study material for online teaching could be split between teachers; students had uninterrupted access to online classes and study material by other teachers; resource sharing made course delivery more robust and resilient.

For next year's course, having accumulated experience from a pilot run, the teachers involved have expressed determination to focus on teaching methodology and didactics, more than the practical considerations which invariably dominate a pilot run.

6 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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